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Review Article

Herbal Cream for Psoriasis, Leucoderma or Vitiligo Disease – A Review

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ABSTRACT

Now a days the demand of herbal Product is increasing day by day. Herbal formulations are receiving more concentration in public because of their high-quality properties and less side effects. The aim of present study was to set the formula for herbal cream by using different herbs such as Bakuchi (Psoralea corylifolia), Neem (Azadirachta indica), Tulsi (Osmium sanctum). The main purpose of our work was to formulate a herbal cream which can produce multipurpose effect, like moisturizer, reduce acne and irritation, reduce skin conditions like psoriasis, eczema, wrinkles, dry skin, rashes etc.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is the science of life. Ayurveda – Ancient Science of Indian Health, since life is synonymous with health, Ayurveda is deemed to be the science of human health. Ayurveda's approach toward shealing is holistic. It doesn't deal with individual organs in isolation, but treats the body as a whole. More important, it doesn't give temporary relief, but fight the disease and help get rid from them. The Ayurvedic Cream vanishes into your skin, rejuvenates and revitalizes your skin from within, leaving it soft, supple and young looking. Its amazing properties range from flavoring curries, to sterilizing wounds, to

grooming women. Now a day's herbal extracts are used in the cosmetic preparations for augmenting beauty and attractiveness. Herbal cosmetics are classified on the basis of dosage form like- cream, powder, soaps, solutions, etc. and according to part or organ of the body to be applied for like; cosmetics for skin, hair, nail, teeth and mouth etc. Bakuchi is used for external application on skin rashes, vitiligo, patches, eczema and to arrest hair fall. Neem is used to promote wound healing, relieves skin dryness, itching and redness and it is also used to reduce pigmentation, reduce acne and pimples. Tulsi is used as antibacterial and can help to prevent the growth of harmful bacteria on the

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skin, which can help to reduce the risk of breakouts and other skin problems.

Cream

Cream are defines as “a semisolid dosage form containing one or more drug substances dissolved or dispersed in a suitable base” Creams are semi-solid emulsions of oil and water. They are of a softer consistency & lighter body than true ointment. Cream are homogeneous, semi-solid or viscous preparations that possess a relatively fluid consistency and are intended for external application to the skin or certain mucous membranes for protective, therapeutic or prophylactic purposes especially where an occlusive dispersions of effect is not necessary. They are semisolids usually consisting of solutions or one or more medicaments in suitable bases. They are formulated using hydrophilic or hydrophobic bases to provide preparations that are essentially miscible with the skin secretion. semisolid emulsions of either O/W or W/O type.

1. Oil in Water O/W
2. Water in Oil W/O
3. Cosmetics cream
4. Medicated cream

Herbal Cream

Herbal creams are the latest, a safe and effective trend in the field of beauty and fashion. These Herbal Creams are gaining popularity as now a days most people prefer natural product so very chemicals for their personal care to enhance their beauty as these products supply the body with nutrients and enhance health and provide satisfaction as these are free from synthetic chemicals, these products supply the body with nutrients and enhance health and provide satisfaction as these are free from synthetic chemicals.

Preparation Of Herbal Cream

Vast types of plants and plant products are used in manufacturing of different types of herbal creams which are intended for different aims of applications. However, all the methods follow some common chain process that can be presented as follows. The process starts with the collection of raw plant materials which after procurement are cleaned and quality assessment of the same are performed. Thereafter depending on need these are dried or processed as such. In the next step the raw plant materials, wherever applicable, are extracted utilizing standard methods and specific solvents or juice/gels are collected using standard methods. The oil phase preparation is the next step where liquid paraffin and beeswax are heated to 75 °C consistently which yields the oil phase to be used in creams. Borax and methyl paraben are mixed with distilled water are heated to 75 °C to create a clear solution. This is known as preparation of aqueous phase. Once the oil phase is heated, gradually water phase is added to it and mixed which is then followed by addition of the herb extract or juices or jelly to yield smooth creams. Finally appropriate aroma is added and the product is ready to be packed.

Common Excipients and Their Roles

Many of different types of excipients are used in the formulations of creams or herbal creams. Few of very common and extensively utilized

excipients are bees wax and liquid paraffin which are used as emulsifier, thickener and lubricating agent. Borax is used in the cosmetic industry to prevent or slow bacterial growth in moisturising products like creams, shampoos, gels, lotions, bath bombs scrubs and bath salts. Manufacturers of cosmetics use borax as a buffering agent or an emulsifier to keep product ingredients from separating. Sodium Benzoate is a commonly used preservative in cosmetics and personal care products. Rose oil as a fragrance. Rose oil is the best face oil for dry skin. It is a natural humectant, meaning it helps to keep the skin hydrated. It does this by drawing moisture from the air and sealing

it into the skin. Water is primarily used as a solvent in cosmetics and personal care products in which it dissolves many of the ingredients that impart skin benefits, such as conditioning agents and cleansing agents. Water also forms emulsions in which the oil and water components of the product are combined to form creams and lotions.

Common Herbs Utilized in Herbal Creams

Many types of herbs are exploited for their different medicinal and cosmetic preparations. Some of the most common in herbal creams are summarized in the following table-

1. Bakuchi extract

2. Neem extract

4. Tulsi extract

Table 1: Common herbs in herbal cream preparations

Common Name	Part used	Chemical Constituents	Uses
Bakuchi	Seeds of <i>Psoralea corylifolia</i>	Psoralen, , Psoralone, Psoralenol, Isopsoralen, bakuchalcone, corylifolean, corylifolin	Psoriasis, Vitiligo, Leucoderma, Dermatoses, Alopecia, Eczema

Neem	Leaves of <i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Nimbidin, Nimbidal, Nimbin, Limonoids	Anti-oxidant, Antiseptic, Anti-ageing, Treats acne
Tulsi	Leaves of <i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Eugenol, Oleanolic Acid, Linalool, Ursolic Acid,	Antimicrobial, Antioxidant, Antiviral, Anti-inflammatory

Disease

- 1. Leucoderma, Or Vitiligo** - A disease that causes the loss of skin colour in blotches. Vitiligo occurs when pigment-producing cells die or stop functioning. Loss of skin colour can affect any part of the body, including the mouth, hair and eyes. It may be more noticeable in people with darker skin. Treatment may improve the appearance of the skin but doesn't cure the disease.
- 2. Psoriasis** - A condition in which skin cells build up and form scales and itchy, dry patches. Psoriasis is thought to be an immune system problem. Triggers include infections, stress and cold. The most common symptom is thick skin patches typically seen on elbows, knees, and lower back associated with white scaling on the scalp. Treatment aims to remove scales and stop skin cells from growing so quickly. Topical ointments, light therapy and medication can offer relief.

CONCLUSION

Natural remedies are more acceptable in the belief that they are safer with fewer side effects than the synthetic ones. The Uses of bioactive ingredient in topical formulations influence biological functions of skins and provide nutrients necessary for the healthy skin. There are various herbs available naturally having different uses in cream preparations. Herbal creams are considered as sustaining and productive way to advance the appearance of skin. They also consist of natural nutrients like Vitamins and minerals that keep skin healthy, glowing and lustrous. Herbal creams are

used to stimulate blood circulation, rejuvenates those muscles and help to maintain the elasticity of the skin and remove dirt from skin pores. During the past few decades herbal formulations have growing demand in the world market and today play a major economic role in the cosmetics industry. More research works towards the safety, efficacy and user compliance in these formulations may lead to more demands of such formulations which will take them through to the peak in global business.

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